

This is a repository copy of “**Silica Nanoparticle addition to control the calcium-leaching in cement-based materials**”

Online URL for this paper: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/pssa.200566168>

Article:

Gaitero, J.J., Sáez de Ibarra, Y., Erkizia, E. and Campillo, I. (2006), Silica nanoparticle addition to control the calcium-leaching in cement-based materials. *phys. stat. sol. (a)*, 203: 1313-1318.

Version:

Accepted Version.

This document is the Accepted Manuscript version of a Published Work that appeared in final form in **Physica Status Solidi a: applications and materials science**. © 2003 WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim.

To access the final edited and published work see:

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/pssa.200566168>

Silica Nanoparticle addition to control the calcium-leaching in cement-based materials

J.J. Gaitero^{*1}, Y. Sáez de Ibarra¹, E. Erkizia¹, and I. Campillo¹

¹ Fundación Labein, C/ Geldo, Edif. 700, Parque Tecnológico de Zamudio, 48160 Derio, Bizkaia, Spain

Received ZZZ, revised ZZZ, accepted ZZZ

Published online ZZZ

PACS 81.07.De, 68.37.Ps, 81.05.Zx

The calcium leaching of the cement hydrated matrix is of vital importance for constructions like water containers, dams, bridges, etc which have to be in contact with water during their lifetime. The aim of this work is the study of the reduction of such a negative phenomenon by the addition of silica nanoparticles. Several characterisation techniques such as ²⁹Si MAS NMR, X-ray diffraction, mercury intrusion porosimetry and EDX-microanalysis have been used to evaluate the effect of the nanoparticles in the cement matrix nanostructure and in their impact on the evolution of the Ca leaching throughout time. Subsequent analysis of the results indicates that silica nanoparticles can reduce the Ca-leaching both decreasing the amount of portlandite in the matrix and controlling the degradation rate of the C-S-H gel.

Introduction

Cement-based materials such as mortars, fibre-reinforced cementitious composites and concrete are by far the most widely used construction materials in the world. However, their omnipresence belies their complexity. They have indeed a truly multi-scalar and multi-phase internal structure. Moreover, cement based materials are “living materials” that keep evolving for centuries, which makes them more susceptible to external attacks. Basically, the cement paste matrix is a porous material composed of calcium hydroxide (Portlandite), aluminates and unhydrated cement (clinker) embedded into an amorphous nano-structured hydration product, the so called C-S-H (Calcium Silicate Hydrate) gel¹ [1]. This gel is the most important hydration product of the cement paste matrix, not only because it is the most abundant component (50 – 70 % by volume), but also because of its exceptionally good mechanical properties. The C-S-H species are poorly crystalline although an organised structure exists at the nanometer scale, which basically consists of silicate chains of varying lengths held together by layers of calcium as shown in Fig. 1. The spatially random stacking of this molecular layered structure causes the apparition of micro-pores, or gel pores as they are also known. With a size of about 1 nm they are actually considered as part of the solid phase and they constitute an important fraction of the total pore volume (~ 28%). Although they can be full of water, this water is bound to the gel and therefore can only be detrimental to the paste through shrinkage if removed by intense drying.

Two other types of pores appear in the cement paste matrix: capillary pores, with sizes on the range of 10 to 100 nm, and macro-pores, with a size of more than 10 μm. The capillary pores, whose radii increase with increasing water/cement ratio, appear between the hydration products, whereas the macropores are due to the presence of entrapped air in the fresh paste during processing. Both of them are detrimental for the overall strength and represent also a path for chemical attacks like the one studied here [1].

Fig.1 Idealised molecular structure of the C-S-H gel.

^{*} Corresponding author: e-mail: jjgaitero@labein.es, Phone: +34 946 073 300, Fax: +34 946 073 349

¹ C = CaO, S = SiO₂ and H = H₂O, commonly used by the cement chemistry community. C-S-H is used as an abbreviation for Calcium Silicate Hydrates at an unspecified mass ratio.

The pH value in the cement matrix is >12.5 , creating a very basic environment. Water that has pH below this level is aggressive to cementitious materials, leading to the dissolution of minerals mainly containing calcium ($\sim 30\%$ of the solid mass in cement paste). This process of dissolution together with the transport of the dissolved calcium in the pore solution is the so-called calcium leaching. The Ca leaching of the cement paste matrix is thus an example of a dissolution mechanism in a porous material. The Ca leaching is controlled by the chemical equilibrium of the calcium-silicate-water system in the cement matrix. According to Berner's diagrams [2], there is a relationship between the C/S-ratio of the hydration products and the amount of calcium in the pore solution. More explicitly, the portlandite is only stable for calcium concentrations higher than 20 mol/m^3 , while the C-S-H gel is stable for values ranging over the interval $2\text{--}20 \text{ mol/m}^3$ depending on its C/S-ratio (the higher the C/S-ratio the higher the value). Silicon rich gels, which are the end product of the degradation process of the C-S-H gel, are stable for values below 2 mol/m^3 .

What happens during the attack is not the same for the portlandite as for the C-S-H gel and other hydration products of minor relevance (not considered thereafter). While the gel dissolves to precipitate afterwards with a lower C/S-ratio, the calcium hydroxide completely disappears into the solution leaving new pores of micrometer size in its place. Kinetics is mainly governed by a two front diffusion-dissolution process [3,4], each of the fronts corresponding to each of the materials attacked by the water. It has been experimentally found that the amount of calcium leached depends almost linearly upon a square root of time [3,5]. This means that it is a very slow rate process, and in consequence this fact makes it necessary the introduction of an accelerated procedure in order to reduce the time of the study. A shift of Berner's curves to higher calcium concentrations enhances the Ca unbalance, which thus increases the dissolution rate. To achieve this, Carde [6,7] replaced water by an ammonium nitrate solution giving rise to a maximum acceleration rate of about 300 for a 6M concentration. Increasing such concentration does not increase the leaching rate any further because at this point the diffusion process completely governs the kinetics.

This work presents preliminary results of a thorough study of the Ca leaching phenomenon in the cement paste matrix with special emphasis on the Ca leaching of the C-S-H gel. It specially addresses the influence of nanosilica addition in the Ca leaching process and attempts to estimate the validity of this addition as a mean of controlling the Ca leaching process and its impact on durability. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work in which ^{29}Si MAS NMR is thoroughly used to study the Ca leaching in cement paste matrices.

Experiments

Three sets of square prismatic samples of $1 \times 1 \times 6 \text{ cm}$ were cast using CEMI 52.5R with a water-cement ratio of 0.5. To one set 1.8% by weight of colloidal silica (CS), with 15 nm particle size, was added. The second one contained a 6% by weight of agglomerated dry silica (ADS) with around $1 \mu\text{m}$ grain size (in the agglomerated form) and 5nm particle size. The last set was left plain (PC) for comparison reasons. All of the samples were demolded after one day of curing in a room at 20°C and 100% humidity and were subsequently immersed into a saturated lime solution at room temperature where they stayed for 27 days. At this time (t_0) the first samples were tested, while the rest were immersed into a 6M ammonium nitrate solution for the accelerated leaching procedure. A gentle shake was periodically applied to the container to avoid concentration gradients and a nitrogen atmosphere was created to reduce carbonation. These samples were finally tested after 10 (t_1), 20 (t_2), 40 (t_3) or 60 (t_4) days depending on the case.

Four different tests were performed in each of the samples: X-ray diffraction, EDX-microanalysis, ^{29}Si MAS NMR and Hg intrusion porosimetry. X-rays were primarily used to monitor the evolution of the crystalline phases of different species (portlandite, unhydrated cement clinker, etc) during the degradation process and at the same time to evaluate the effect of the nano-additions over such species. The C/S-ratio evolution was followed by EDX-microanalysis. ^{29}Si MAS NMR was used to measure the connectivity of the silicate species in the C-S-H gel. Silicon atoms in a silicate cluster can be connected to 1, 2, 3 or 4 Si atoms by an O atom, each connection giving place to a different peak in the NMR spectra, see Fig. 2, plus a peak that corresponds to the Si atom in a single silicate tetrahedron.

Fig. 2 Connectivity of silicon in silicate species. Q_i means tetrahedrally coordinated Si atom with i bridging oxygens.

Results and discussion

Fig. 3 shows the X-ray diffraction patterns obtained for the different samples at t_0 (left) and at t_1 (right). It can be noticed at t_0 that the effect of the addition of silica nanoparticles to a cement paste matrix reduces the amount of portlandite within the paste by means of a pozzolanic reaction [1]. However, this effect is not apparent in the case of the colloidal dispersion, presumably because of the small quantity used. Once the aggressive attack begins, the peaks of the calcium hydroxide begin to decrease, indicating that the dissolution process has begun. Ten days later, at t_1 , the peaks have completely disappeared, which means that there is no more portlandite left. After t_1 , all calcium containing compounds are slowly consumed till barely anything remains after 60 days.

Fig. 3 X-ray diffraction pattern of the three sets at t_0 (left) and t_1 (right).

Measures of the Ca/Si ratio as a function of time are displayed in Figure 4. They show a completely different behaviour in the case of the ADS samples compared to the other ones. While the C/S ratio barely changes from t_0 (0 days) to t_1 (10 days) in ADS samples, an important drop can be observed for both the plain cement matrix and the matrix modified by CS. This is in complete agreement with the results from the X-rays, since the first Ca leaching in the matrix is that of portlandite [10], being the amount of portlandite lower in the ADS samples (see Fig. 3) because of the pozzolanic reaction. In this reaction portlandite reacts with the silica giving rise to C-S-H gel which leaches at a lower rate than portlandite. Therefore the matrix leaches Ca at a lower rate in the first stages of the process in ADS samples. However, it is very surprising that the addition of silica to the cement produces an increase on the Ca/Si ratio at every measurement, which can only be explained by experimental error in this type of measurements, though further work is needed.

Fig. 4 Ca/Si ratio evolution as a function of time.

In Figure 5, the evolution of porosity for the different samples is displayed as a function of time. The study of the porosity shows, again, a different behaviour in the case of the ADS samples than in the other samples. While the plain cement paste and the paste with CS addition reach their maximum values (slightly bigger for the PC than the CS) after 10 days, it takes 20 days to the ADS to reach the 50% porosity limit. This sudden increase of the porosity in the first days is a consequence of the portlandite leaching, which leaves behind pores of the sizes of the portlandite crystals. The ADS sample begins at lower porosity and it shows a slower increase rate as the leaching evolves, since the pozzolanic reaction yields a more compact matrix due to the portlandite consumption as explained before. After reaching the 50% limit, the porosity stabilises due to the fact that the contribution of the C-S-H gel porosity change by the Ca leaching is out of the range of the Hg intrusion porosimetry. Therefore, it is the evolution of portlandite what is observed, confirming the results of the previous techniques.

Fig. 5 Porosity evolution as a function of time.

Finally, in Figures 6 and 7 ^{29}Si MAS NMR results are displayed. The first thing that becomes apparent is the lack of the Q_3 and Q_4 peaks for all the samples at t_0 (Fig. 6a), which evidences the complete reaction of the nanosilica. It is also observed that Ca-leaching induces a polymerization of the silicon species to a Q_3 type connectivity (the chemical shift ranges from -90 to -100 ppm in hydrated cement [11] for Q_3) which is much more important in the plain cement paste matrix than in the silica modified pastes. This is evident from Fig. 6b, and from Fig. 7 which shows that the Q_3/Q_2 ratio is at 20 days two times higher for the plain paste than for the nanosilica modified pastes. Furthermore, a lower increase for the Q_3/Q_2 ratio is observed for the nanosilica modified pastes as the Ca leaching takes place. In fact it remains almost constant, whereas for the plain cement paste the ratio increases by a 66 %. Therefore the silicate polymerisation that accompanies the Ca leaching takes place at a very lower rate in nanosilica modified cement matrices. This is very remarkable because it means that the silica nanoparticles modify the C-S-H gel in such a way that the Ca leaching can be controlled at the C-S-H gel level.

Fig. 6 ^{29}Si MAS NMR spectra at t_0 (left) and at t_3 (right).

Fig. 7 Q₃/Q₂ ratio evolution as a function of time.

Conclusions

A coherent set of data from different characterisation techniques has been collected on the study of the Ca leaching phenomenon in cement paste matrices. These results confirm that portlandite consumption occurs in the early stage of accelerated Ca leaching. The pozzolanic reaction induced by the addition of 6% by weight of cement of agglomerated dry silica prevents this early Ca leaching. ²⁹Si MAS NMR results indicate that silicate polymerisation of the C-S-H gel induced by Ca leaching in nanosilica modified cement pastes is far less intense than in blank cement pastes. Finally it can be concluded that nanosilica addition to cement-based materials can control C-S-H degradation induced by Ca leaching.

Acknowledgements The authors wish to thank the financial support from the Basque Government via the ETORTEK Program under NANOMAT IE031 Project from the department of Industry, Trade and Tourism, the Diputación Foral de Vizkaia via the Bizkaitek program and the Fundación Centros Tecnológicos-Iñaki Goenaga via a PhD grant.

References

- [1] H.F.W. Taylor, Cement chemistry (Thomas Telford – Second edition, 1997).
- [2] U.R. Berner, Radiochimica acta, **44/45**, 387-393 (1988).
- [3] F. Adenot, PhD. dissertation, University of Orleans, France (1992).
- [4] F.J. Ulm, E. Lemarchard and F.H. Heukamp, Engineering fracture mechanics, **70** (7-8), 871-889 (2003).
- [5] F.H. Heukamp and F.J. Ulm, PhD. Dissertation, M.I.T, Massachusetts, U.S.A. (2002).
- [6] C. Carde, Cement and concrete research, **26** (8), 1257-1268 (1996).
- [7] C. Carde, Cement and concrete research, **27** (4), 539-550 (1997).
- [8] A.R. Brough, C.M. Dobson, I.G. Richardson and G.W. Groves, Journal of Materials Science **29**, 3926-3940 (1994).
- [9] X. Cong and R. Kirkpatrick, Advanced Cement Based Materials **3**, 133-143 (1996).
- [10] F.H. Heukamp, F.J. Ulm and J.T. Germaine, Cement and concrete research **33** (8), 1155-1173 (2003).
- [11] V.S. Ramachandran and J.J. Beaudoin, Handbook of analytical techniques in concrete. (William Andrew Publishing, New York, 2001).